

Acid Hydrazides as Ligands.

IV. Metal Complexes of Phenyl Acetyl Hydrazides

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Metal complexes of phenylacetylhydrazide are reported. Electronic spectra—solid and solution—of manganese(II), iron(II), nickel(II), copper(II), zinc(II), palladium(II) and cadmium complexes, and i.r. spectra of deuterated and non-deuterated complexes in the range 1700–700 cm^{-1} are incorporated. The ligand is monodentate and the coordination site is the amide nitrogen. Other physical properties of complexes are also reported.

The authors have previously described metal complexes of malondihydrazide, succindihydrazide, acetylhydrazide and benzoylhydrazide. The amide nitrogen atoms have been suggested to be the coordination sites¹⁻³. The present communication will discuss i.r. spectra of complexes and some of the deuterated complexes in the range 1700–700 cm^{-1} and visible reflectance spectra of mull and solution of metal complexes of phenyl acetyl hydrazide.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of phenylacetylhydrazide (PAH): The ligand was prepared⁴ by refluxing equimolecular mixture of corresponding ethyl ester and hydrazine hydrate (80%) on water bath till the disappearance of separation of layers. On cooling, white fine needle shaped crystal separated which was recrystallised from slightly warmed ethanol, desolvated and analysed m.p. 116°. The ligand is soluble in ethanol, methanol and water and insoluble in ether. The ligand on refluxing with ethanol forms diphenylacetylhydrazide.

Preparation of metal complexes: The methods of preparation of the complexes were the same as methods described earlier¹⁻³.

Preparation of the N-deuterated ligand and complexes: The methods of preparation of the complexes were the same as methods described earlier^{2,3}.

Physical measurements and other experimental details: These were same as described in previous publications.

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RESULTS

Analysis data of the complexes along with their colour and m.p./d.p. are presented in Table I. From the data it appears that the ligand produces cationic complexes, the charge of which neutralised by association with anion which may be coordinated to the metal atom. The isolated complexes may be described as ML_x^{+2} ,

$x = 1$ for Mn(II), Fe(II) and Cd(II)

$x = 2$ for Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II) and Pd(II).

The complexes are soluble in water. Only palladium complex is insoluble in water.

TABLE I

Analysis^a Data of Metal Complexes of Phenylacetylhydrazide

Complexes	Colour	Metal	Nitrogen	Chlorine	Sulphur	m.p./d.p. (°C)	eff ^b	Molar conduc- tance ^c (mho/cm) in water
MnLCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	White	17.63 (17.60)	9.00 (8.97)	22.45 (22.75)		104 ^d	5.76	211.7
FeLSO ₄ ·4H ₂ O	White	14.67 (14.94)	7.35 (7.49)		8.44 (8.55)	180	5.24	263.8
NiL ₂ Cl ₂ ·3H ₂ O	Blue	12.33 (12.13)	11.65 (11.58)	14.69 (14.69)		245	3.13	177.2
CuL ₂ SO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	Blue	13.15 (12.83)	11.27 (11.30)		6.84 (6.46)	237	1.96	225.2
ZnL ₂ SO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	White	13.16 (13.14)	11.14 (11.26)		6.29 (6.43)	205		185.9
PdL ₂ Cl ₂ ·H ₂ O	Yellow	21.09 (21.51)	11.06 (11.20)	14.31 (14.51)		185		36.8 ^e
CdLCl ₂	White	34.31 (33.72)	8.45 (8.40)	21.06 (21.29)		240 ^d		207.3

a. Figures in parentheses are the required percentages.

b. Diamagnetic correction per ligand molecule— 79.23×10^{-6} c.g.s. unit.

c. $\sim 10^{-3}M$ solution at 24°.

d. Except these cases all are d.p.

e. Molar conductance in methanol.

The summary and some probable assignments of infrared bands of PAH and its complexes and their deuterated analogues are presented in Table II. It is apparent that Amide I and $\beta(NH_2)$ are overlapping in PAH which get separated in complexes. The bands at ~ 1650 cm^{-1} in complexes are Amide I band which remain unaltered on deuteration. The Amide II (1587 cm^{-1}) of the ligand is almost stationary in complexes. This band and the one at ~ 1600 cm^{-1} in complexes disappeared in deuteration. The latter possibly is $\beta(NH_2)$ in the complexes. The band at 1495 cm^{-1} and at ~ 1220 cm^{-1} of the ligand may be assigned to Amide II' and $\beta(ND_2)$ respectively. The Amide III band of the ligand at 1260 cm^{-1} .

TABLE II
Infrared spectra of Complexes of PAH and PAH-d₃ (in nujol mull)

Possible assignment	P.A.H.	P.A.H.-d ₃	MnLCl ₂ , 2H ₂ O	Mn(L-d ₃)Cl ₂	NiL ₂ Cl ₂ , 3H ₂ O	Ni(L-d ₃) ₂ Cl ₂	CuL ₂ SO ₄ , 2H ₂ O	ZnL ₂ SO ₄ , 2H ₂ O	PdL ₂ Cl ₂ , H ₂ O	CdLCl ₂
Amide I and β(NH ₂)	1635 s	1600 sh	1660 sh	1660 sh	1662 m	1660 sh	1662 m	1640 s	1675 s	1650 sh
		1640 s	1625 sb	1625 sb	1630 s	1630 s	1650 sh	1630 w	1640 s	1638 s
β(NH ₂) Amide II	1587 s		1608 s	1600 m	1650 sh	1600 m	1580 w	1602 m	1607 w	1607 w
			1582 m	1590 m	1600 m	1590 m	1565 ms	1590 m	1591 m	1591 m
			1575 m		1535 m		1552 m		1550 vw	
Amide II'	1520 ms	1535 m	1535 w	1535 m	1535 m	1535 m	1532 w	1522 w	1540 m	1515 w
		1480 m	1492 m	1490 w	1490 w	1490 m	1490 m	1490 w	1500 w	1490 w
NH ₂ -def.	1410 m	1410 ms	1420 ms	1410 ms	1408 ms	1408 ms	1405 w	1410 m	1392 m	1320 w
	1342 m	1300 m	1260 m	1290 w	1315 m	1298 m	1280 sh	1280 wb	1340 sh	
β(ND ₂)	1260 m	1260 m	1260 m	1260 vw	1260 w	1260 w	1200 w	1285 w	1275 w	
	1240 sh	1200 wm	1218 wm	1205 wm	1170 m	1205 sh	1205 sh	1225 wb	1255 w	
NH ₂ -def.	1192 w	1158 wm	1158 wm	1158 wm	1142 m	1140 sh	1140 sh	1190 sh	1160 w	1165 w
		1132 wm	1112 w	1110 sb	1090 s	1090 s	1070 s	1070 s	1110 s	1115 m
ND ₂ -def. NH ₂ -def.	1070 m	1070 m	1060 wm	1065 w	1070 wm	1065 s	1040 m	1070 s	1065 vw	1065 w
		1040 m	1040 m	1045 m	1030 wm	1030 ms	1030 ms	1047 m	1047 m	1040 w
Amide III	1027 m	1005 m	1005 m	1020 w	1010 wm	1010 sh	1000 m	1030 ms	960 } bb	955 w
	997 ms	988 m	988 m	975 wm	992 wm	982 sh	982 sh	960 m	950 }	
ND ₂ -def.	950 wb	910 w	912 wm	912 w	912 w	880 w	910 vw	965 m	960 m	960 m
		830 w	830 w	830 w	825 m	825 m	880 w	935 wm	935 wm	910 w
ND ₂ -def. δ(NCO)	772 m	765 m	765 m	770 w	765 sh	775 wb	775 wb	770 w	755 m	780 w
	758 w	705 s	705 s	710 m	738 sh	715 s	720 ms	710 m	715 m	730 m
	705 s	680 w	680 w	682 m	702 s	692 ms	682 m	682 m	691 m	680 m

possibly corresponds to 962 cm^{-1} in PAH- d_3 . In complexes the band is observed at slightly higher wave number which on deuteration has disappeared. The other NH_2 deformation vibrations may be assigned to bands at 1342 cm^{-1} , 1158 cm^{-1} and 1027 cm^{-1} and the corresponding vibrations in deuterated ligand are observed at 1040 cm^{-1} , 870 cm^{-1} and 810 cm^{-1} respectively. In complexes these vibrations are almost stationary or shifts slightly to higher wave number. Another significant fact is that the band at $\sim 772\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 757 cm^{-1} is not displaced on deuteration (one band at PAH- d_3 at 765 cm^{-1}) but are displaced in complexes to $\sim 720\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which are again unaltered on deuteration of the complexes.

Magnetic moments show high spin character for all the complexes concerned (Table I).

Table III presents a summary of visible spectral data of complexes of PAH recorded in solid and in aqueous solution as well as with excess ligand.

TABLE III

Visible spectral Data of Metal Complexes of Phenylacetylhydrazide

		λ_{max} ($m\mu$)	Wave number (cm^{-1})	ϵ_{max}
$\text{MnLCl}_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Aqua	Weak visible absorption		
$\text{FeLSO}_4, 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Aqua	Weak visible absorption		
$\text{NiL}_2\text{Cl}_2, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Aqua	590	16949	5.7
		700	14285	2.8
		760	13158	2.4
		950	10526	7.9
$\text{NiL}_2\text{Cl}_2, 3\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{L}$	Aqua	575	17391	6.6
		740	13514	2.7
		925	10811	8.6
$\text{NiL}_2\text{Cl}_2, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Refl.	607	16474	
		826	11107	
		1027	9759	
$\text{CuL}_2\text{SO}_4, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Aqua	715	13986	26.6
$\text{CuL}_2\text{SO}_4, 2\text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{L}$	Aqua	690	14493	33.0
$\text{CuL}_2\text{SO}_4, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Mull	600	16667	
		630	15873	
$\text{PdL}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$		380	26316	300.3
$\text{PdL}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{L}$	MeOH	395	25316	371.0
$\text{PdL}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{H}_2\text{O}$	DMF	390	25641	360.1
$\text{PdL}_2\text{Cl}_2, \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{L}$	DMF	365	27397	967.7

Conductance data are displayed in Table I and are consistent with the values expected for 1 : 2 electrolyte.

λ_{max} values of ultraviolet absorption spectra of PAH and its complexes in water (methanol in case of palladium complex only) are summarised in Table IV. Both the high intensity and low intensity bands are almost stationary in complexes. In iron complex the intensities are too low and in palladium complex both the bands undergo slight red shift.

TABLE IV

Ultraviolet spectral Data of Metal Complexes of Phenylacetylhydrazide

Complexes	λ_{max} (m μ)	ϵ_{max}
PAH	211	6237.0
	257	208.0
MnLCl ₂ , 2H ₂ O	211	5873.5
	257	396.5
FeLSO ₄ , 4H ₂ O	214	1131.0
	257	219.9
NiL ₂ Cl ₂ , 3H ₂ O	215	7991.3
	257	84.3
CuL ₂ SO ₄ , 2H ₂ O	215	7340.0
	255	1040.0
ZnLSO ₄ , 2H ₂ O	214	8417.1
	257	91.8
PdL ₂ Cl ₂ , H ₂ O	220	1699.7
	275	5615.0
CdLCl ₂	211	5636.6
	257	332.6

The pK_a value of PAH is 3.14 for the equilibrium, $LH^+ \rightleftharpoons L + H^+$.

DISCUSSION

Infrared spectra: The band characteristics of PAH and its complexes and their deuterated analogues are closely similar to the corresponding cases of MDH and SDH. The basic rationale of interpretation have been discussed in detail in the paper^{1,2} and it may be concluded that the ligand is monodentate and the coordination site is the amide nitrogen (N²). The shift of $\delta(NCO)$ band to lower wave number is the direct evidence.

Magnetic moment: Moment of nickel complex is typical of octahedral configuration. Manganese, iron and copper complexes show the normally expected moments.

Visible spectra: Visible spectra of nickel complex is typical of octahedral configuration. The first $d \rightarrow d$ transition moves progressively towards higher energy from reflectance to aqueous solution with excess ligand through aqueous solution only. The effect is similar to those observed with complexes of malondihydrazide, succindihydrazide, acetylhydrazide, and benzoylhydrazide. The observations are, therefore, similar to those observed in the previous paper¹⁻³. Corresponding to the spectra in solid state, 10 Dq values for full occupation of coordination positions by six ligands (hypothetical ML_6^{+2}) is $\sim 13000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ considering monodentate character of ligand, and aqua and/or chlorine coordination. The value is slightly high, but considering the approximate nature of calculation and stronger donor

capacity, the value is comparable to those of AH and BH. This also suggests monodentate character of PAH and coordination through the amide nitrogen atom. The $d \rightarrow d$ transition of copper complex moves towards lower energy in solution compared to those in solid state. The present spectral evidences, however, do not point to any unequivocal stereochemistry. Palladium complex shows absorption maximum close to the u.v. region and possibly merge with the charge transfer band. The bands are susceptible to excess ligand as well as solvent. The π -interactions, if there is any, is not significant in both the cases.

Conductance, UV spectra and pK value : Conductance values of nickel and zinc are slightly low. The values may indicate the relative degree of equation. The UV spectra of the ligand and the complexes show that $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition at $211 \sim 215 m\mu$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition at $\sim 260 m\mu$. The $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition is virtually unchanged while the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition has undergone a slight bathochromic shift in complexes. The shift is little more in palladium complex. The pK_a values also indicate that protonation has nothing to do with carbonyl oxygen^{1,2}.

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